

Role of Antibiotic Impregnated Calcium Sulfate Beads in Treatment of Paediatric Chronic Osteomyelitis

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Abstract:

Background: In cases of persistent osteomyelitis, calcium sulfate impregnated with antibiotics provides excellent therapeutic efficacy. Its ability to treat paediatric chronic osteomyelitis, however, has not received enough research attention. This study aimed to assess the potential therapeutic benefits of calcium sulfate impregnated with antibiotics for the management of juvenile chronic osteomyelitis.

Methods: Ten paediatric cases with chronic osteomyelitis who received care at our facility between January 2022 and December 2023 in total were included for evaluation. An analysis was conducted on the clinical history, clinical manifestation, pathological fractures, bone growth, surgical operations and rate of infection recurrence, leakage from sinuses and incisions.

Results: After at least a year of follow-up, there was no infection recurrence, no osteolysis. In one paediatric case, incision site leakage occurred and one had non-union and limb shortening occurred.

Conclusion: In paediatric chronic osteomyelitis, antibiotic-impregnated calcium sulfate had a satisfactory therapeutic effect, despite the occurrence of non-infectious sequelae.

Keywords: Paediatric Chronic Osteomyelitis, Calcium Sulfate Beads.

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Introduction

Osteomyelitis is an inflammatory disorder of bone caused by infection leading to necrosis and destruction [1]. Recent decades have seen a rise in the occurrence of osteomyelitis, which has a major socioeconomic impact [2]. One type of osteomyelitis known as hematogenous osteomyelitis occurs when bacteria enter the bone by hematogenous seeding. For Chronic cases, surgical intervention is the way to stop the condition from getting worse [3].

Decompression, removal of necrotic tissue, sequestrectomy, irrigation, and aspiration are examples of surgical interventions [4]. Addressing the bone loss brought on by surgery, Nonabsorbable bone filler polymethylmethacrylate (PMMA) has been shown to have good therapeutic results in paediatric Chronic Osteomyelitis (CO).

When nonabsorbable polymethylmethacrylate (PMMA) + antibiotics were put in the bones, it was found to have satisfactory curative benefits in chronic paediatric osteomyelitis [5]. But there are drawbacks as well: PMMA is not biodegradable, it inhibits bone regrowth, and it usually necessitates a second surgical surgery to remove the beads and then transplant bone [6–8]. Calcium sulfate (CS), on the other hand, is osteoconductive, does not require a removal process, and can be impregnated

with antibiotics. Moreover, CS has a well-established clinical history as a bone void filler [9–12]. Common options for CS loading include tobramycin, vancomycin, and gentamicin [13]. Paediatric CO patients have been treated with antibiotic-impregnated CS pellets, with positive results reported in studies [14, 15]. The purpose of this study was to further discuss our experience with antibiotic-impregnated CS and its effectiveness in treating paediatric CO.

Methods

Study Design and Setting: A case series analysis was conducted on paediatric CO patients who received care at our hospital between January 2022 and December 2023. The following were the primary criteria for inclusion: 1) Patients under the age of eighteen; 2) Patients with CO treated with CS beads following surgical intervention; and 3) Patients continuing to be monitored for follow-up.

The following were the primary exclusion criteria: patients with internal fixation infections or direct spreading osteomyelitis, such as postoperative osteomyelitis; 2) patients undergoing soft tissue surgery; and 3) patients lost to follow-up. Based on a positive culture or Peltola and Vahvanen's definition [16], osteomyelitis was diagnosed.

Demographics, clinical history, aetiology, imaging data, osteomyelitis site, operation procedure, and follow-up time were among the clinical data gathered. Serum inflammatory indices comprised white blood cell count (WBC), erythrocyte sedimentation rate (ESR), and C-reactive protein (CRP) level.

Descriptions of the Surgery: The surgical technique was guided by preoperative imaging and employed the safest, most direct way to debride all foci of infection. Abscesses, subperiosteal tissues, and deep soft-tissue collections were removed. A cortical window was made at the infection's epicentre in patients with long bone osteomyelitis to provide access to the area. Using the appropriate curette, intramedullary abscesses were removed, and the surrounding

physis was carefully protected. The abscesses and/or lesions were sent for bacterial culture and biopsies. Subsequently, CS impregnated with antibiotics was used to bridge the gap and administer regional antibiotics. Using the manufacturers supplied solvent, one gram of vancomycin (or 240 mg of gentamicin or 240mg tobramycin) and ten millilitres of CS were thoroughly mixed until a smooth paste was formed (about thirty seconds).

After mixing, the paste was let at least 15 minutes to set without being disturbed. The size of the bone defect determined the quantity of beads required. Tensionless Sutures were put to the skin. After decompression, if the bone was unstable, an External fixator or Slab was applied. In situations when there were significant bone abnormalities, bone transport technology was used.

Figure 1: 10yr old boy with fibula osteomyelitis treated with Sequestrectomy and Calcium Sulfate Beads Antibiotic Beads

Figure 2: 7 yr old boy treated with Curettage and Calcium Sulfate Antibiotic Beads

Figure 3: A 4-year-old boy with chronic Osteomyelitis treated with Curettage, Calcium Sulfate Antibiotic Beads, JESS FIXATOR and Intramedullary K-WIRE

After care and Follow-up: Intraoperative intravenous antibiotics were routinely administered to every patient. The average length of time that intravenous antibiotics were given was 7.41 days. After that, oral antibiotics were given for about two weeks. Once the patients' symptoms subsided, they were discharged. In outpatient department, we conducted routine Follow-up of the patients and conducted telephonic Reviews.

A worsening of the clinical illness, steadily rising blood inflammatory markers, the development of a sinus tract, and/or persistent bone tissue deterioration on Radiographs were considered indicators of an infection recurrence. When clinical, laboratory, or radiological signs of infection were absent at the time of the last medical visit (for patients with at least 1 year of follow-up), or when there was no longer a need for reoperation or the administration of an additional course of antibiotic therapy for the same site after the end of therapy, we classified patients as being in remission of infection.

Results

The average age of the seven males and three girls who were considered for assessment was 9.50 years

(range: 3–15 years). Four cases had Chronic Osteomyelitis at Tibia, Two at femur, two at Humerus, one at the radius, and one at the Fibula. The range of the onset time was 4.5–30 months, with an average of 8.32 months. WBC count ranged from 6.43 to 11.07 * 10 /L, with an average of 7.76 * 10 /L. ESR ranged from 25 to 71 mm/L, with an average of 41.14 mm/L. 13.35 mg/L on average (range: 1.23–37.04 mg/L) was the CRP. This study includes ten participants with CO. The cause was identified as *S. aureus* in four patients, Methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* (MRSA) in three patients and *Enterobacter cloacae* (*E. cloacae*) in one patient. In two cases, the culture was negative. All of the patients had their infections completely eradicated, and the rate of infection recurrence was zero, no osteolysis.

Three of these patients had previously used traditional Desi/Chinese treatment. Out of these three patients, one had incision site leakage postoperatively for about a week and another one had a pathological fracture which was managed with thorough Curettage, CS Beads, JESS fixator and Intramedullary K-Wire

Initially Postoperative Radiographs of this case showed a good outcome.

Figure 4:

However subsequently, infection was controlled but Non-union and Limb Shortening by 6 cm occurred.

Figure 5:

Table 1

S.NO	AGE/SEX	BONE	SIDE	SYMPTOMS	PROCEDURE*	CULTURE	COMPLICATIONS
1	10y/M	Fibula	L	Pain, Swelling	Sequestrectomy	S. aureus	Incision Site Leakage
2	3y/M	Humerus	R	Pain, Sinus, Fever	Curettage	MRSA	-
3	13.5y/F	Tibia	L	Pain, Swelling	Sequestrectomy + Bone Transport	S. aureus	-
4	15y/M	Femur	R	Pain, Sinus	Sequestrectomy + External Fixator	MRSA	-
5	7y/M	Tibia	L	Pain, Swelling	Curettage	Negative	-
6	7.5y/M	Radius	L	Pain	Curettage	MRSA	-
7	11y/F	Tibia	R	Pain, Swelling	Sequestrectomy + Bone Transport	Negative	-
8	4y/M	Humerus	L	Pain, Sinus, Pathological Fracture	Curettage + JESS Fixator + K-Wire	S. aureus	Non- Union, Limb Shortening
9	12.5y/F	Tibia	R	Pain, Sinus	Sequestrectomy	E. cloacae	-
10	11.5y/M	Femur	L	Pain	Sequestrectomy + External Fixator	S. aureus	-

*Antibiotic Impregnated Calcium Sulfate Beads were used in all cases

Discussion

One kind of paediatric musculoskeletal infection is called Chronic Osteomyelitis, where Surgical intervention is used to stop the disease from getting worse [3]. Among paediatric musculoskeletal infections, CO is the most challenging illness to comprehend and it poses a major clinical issue [18]. In 2009, Copley et al. [4] described a surgical strategy for intramedullary abscesses that included

bone decompression and curettage. They did not, however, address how to fill the space created by surgery.

In 2010, Bar-On et al. [5] reported that intramedullary reaming and antibiotic-impregnated PMMA were efficacious treatments for four patients with chronic juvenile osteomyelitis. In the

case of paediatric osteomyelitis, this was the first report of a nonabsorbable local antibiotic release mechanism.

In 2019, Antonio Andreacchio et al. [14] reported that debridement and filling with antibiotic-impregnated CS successfully treated twelve juvenile patients with persistent osteomyelitis. This was the first report of a paediatric osteomyelitis case using an absorbable local antibiotic delivery device. Vikas Ellur et al. [15] reported the successful treatment of thirty-four paediatric patients with chronic osteomyelitis by debridement and filling with antibiotic-impregnated CS in 2021. We present the effective treatment of ten paediatric patients with CO using debridement, decompression and antibiotic-impregnated CS beads in our study. Our research offers a more thorough understanding of the use of CS in CO and serves as a supplement to these earlier investigations. A two-step surgical procedure was suggested by Masquelet [19] to treat persistent osteomyelitis. Sharp debridement of necrotic tissue, copious lavage, sequestrectomy, and removal of any hardware and/or foreign substances are the initial steps. PMMA infused with antibiotics is then administered. The second stage is a separate surgical procedure that is necessary for the beads to be removed and for the bone graft to follow.

Despite demonstrating a remarkable therapeutic impact in the eradication of infection, the use of antibiotic-impregnated PMMA has been reduced over years. First, because PMMA is non-biodegradable, it may act as a reservoir for recurrent infection if it is left in the void after the time when antibiotic elution is effective [20, 21]. Secondly, PMMA hinders bone development and needs to be removed surgically, which is the second step. The second procedure increases overall cost and causes a delay in the healing process [22]. Other drawbacks of PMMA treatment include a higher chance of the emergence of bacteria resistant to antibiotics and a weakened host immune system [20,23,24].

Furthermore, the application of autogenous iliac bone grafting is associated with donor site problems, including fatigue fractures, infection, and instability [22]. As a result, CS has gained therapeutic attention as an absorbable substance. The benefits of antibiotic-impregnated CS are distinct. It first demonstrates the typical slow and steady resorption, is osteoconductive, and gets absorbed thereby preventing need for subsequent surgery [25–27]. Second, it has been discovered that antibiotic-impregnated CS is osteoinductive, indicating that it can cause bone marrow mesenchymal stem cells to differentiate into osteoblasts [28]. Furthermore, it has been discovered that CS impregnated with antibiotics induces the development of a vascularized

membrane, which can inhibit graft resorption and produce an environment that is conducive to vascularization and corticalization, so encouraging the bone formation [29]. All ten of the patients in our study had the infection completely cleared, and just one patient had non-union of the pathological fracture. These outcomes validated the antibiotic-impregnated CS's healing ability to completely eradicate the illness. Although any water-soluble antibiotic can be put into CS, the ideal antibiotic remains contentious. Commonly used antibiotics for CS loading are vancomycin, gentamicin, and tobramycin. CS impregnated with vancomycin and tobramycin demonstrated comparable germicidal qualities and elution efficiency in an in vitro experiment [11]. Additionally, a systematic analysis found that the frequency of surgical complications and the eradication rate in patients with chronic osteomyelitis were unaffected by the choice of antibiotic, that is tobramycin-loaded CS or vancomycin combined with gentamicin-loaded CS [13]. For patients without reliable bacterial information, the selection of a local antibiotic is based on the local epidemiological data. For gram-positive patients or those who had a strong suspicion of having a *S. aureus* infection, we empirically selected vancomycin, and for gram-negative individuals, gentamicin. For individuals whose bacterial infections were difficult to diagnose, we empirically selected vancomycin and gentamicin combination.

Local antibiotics have special benefits over long-term intravenous antibiotics. One benefit of local antibiotic treatments over intravenous antibiotics is the ability to obtain higher and more effective concentrations in the local area of infected bone. Another is the decreased risk of systemic toxicity and the avoidance of side effects associated with systemic chemotherapy [30]. 24 osteomyelitis patients received treatment with vancomycin-impregnated CS beads (a dose range from 1.5 ml to 5 ml at a ratio of 1 g of vancomycin: 5 ml of calcium sulfate), and Zhang et al. [31] examined the blood vancomycin levels of these patients. The findings demonstrated that the mean blood vancomycin level remained within an application-safe range. According to P. Wahl et al. [32], when 6 g of vancomycin was administered locally, both the local concentration and the systemic concentration were still below the established limits for cellular toxicity. The systemic concentration stayed within a safe range. Patients in our study received oral and intravenous antibiotics for a brief period of time. There were no side effects associated with systemic chemotherapy.

According to Ping-change Leung et al. [33], the topical administration of traditional Chinese medicine showed positive outcomes in treating de-Quervain's disease, plantar fasciitis, tennis elbow,

and undisplaced metatarsal fractures. The benefits of topical traditional Chinese medicine administration, according to the authors, include pain alleviation and inflammatory management. However, the skin condition was not described by the writers. In our study, the parents of three patients who had never had surgery before administered topical traditional Chinese medicine. One of these patients had surgical site leakage afterwards. One of the drawbacks of CS is aseptic exudation [30, 34]. Fluid flow from the incision or surgical site is a frequently reported observation linked to the surgical use of CS; it happens in 4% to 51% of patients [11, 22, 35]. There have been reports of fluid discharge for anywhere between two and twenty-four weeks [35]. The fluid discharge in our investigation lasted for around one week. We speculate that topical administration of traditional Chinese medicine may cause skin damage and raise the possibility of aseptic exudation and sinusitis brought on by CS. Solving the urgent problem of preventing aseptic exudation following the use of antibiotic-impregnated CS is imperative. Given this, we provide the following guidance based on our personal experience: 3. Do not apply topical traditional Chinese medicine; 2. Position the CS in a region rich in soft tissue; and 3. Avoid getting the CS overly wet. The most common side effect of internal fixation and complete joint replacement is osteolysis [36, 37]. The following are the primary mechanisms that causes osteolysis: 1. inflammation brought on by inflammatory stimuli; 2. inflammation brought on by innate immune receptor stimulation; 3. inflammation brought on by debris; 4. Bone resorption linked to inflammation [37]. Bone grafting utilizing bone allografts, bone-graft replacements (such as different osteoconductive or osteoinductive materials), or combinations of these is the treatment for osteolysis [38]. CS was created as an alternative to bone grafts for the treatment of osteolysis. There were no cases of osteolysis in our study. However earlier studies by Rui Tao et al hypothesized that this could occur due to two factors: 1. stimulation brought on by the vancomycin-impregnated CS; and 2. stimulation brought on by bone decompression and debridement.[41]

Systemic and local hormonal mechanisms, as well as mechanical loads, have been identified to impact bone development [39]. A major problem that occurred in one of the individuals in our study was non-union of the pathological fracture. We think that unusually retarded bone growth may have been caused by these systemic and local hormonal mechanisms and genetic factors.

The process of creating new bone between vascular bone surfaces established by an osteotomy and gradually distracting them is known as the "bone

transport technique" [40]. This method was used to treat two individuals in our study who had significant bone abnormalities. Thankfully, these individuals had good outcome.

Limitations

This study was limited in several ways. Firstly, comparisons were not made to validate the findings. Secondly, only ten patients were included in this study. The 100% infection eradication rate and the rarity of consequences, however, are data that can support the conclusions of previous research. Large-sample randomized controlled trials are anticipated to validate our results.

Conclusion

While non-infectious side effects like Non-union and incision site leakage can occur, antibiotic-impregnated CS proved to be a good treatment for paediatric CO.

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